

Impact of E-Marketing on Achieving the Competitive Advantage: Evidence from Bahrain

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Abstract:- This research aims to know the impact of E-Marketing (reliability, response and safety) on achieving the competitive advantage at Batelco Company in the Kingdom of Bahrain. Four hundred customers were surveyed through a simple random sample method. The analysis depends on the outcomes of the questionnaire survey that was given out to a representative sample of the customers of the company in question. The researchers hypothesized that there is a positive significant impact for E-Marketing (reliability, response and safety) on achieving the competitive advantage at Batelco Company in the Kingdom of Bahrain. The findings revealed that there was a positive significant impact or E-Marketing (reliability, response and safety) on achieving the competitive advantage at Batelco Company in the Kingdom of Bahrain. In addition, the results showed that there were no statistically significant differences relating to the impact of E-Marketing (reliability, response and safety) on achieving the competitive advantage at Batelco Company in the Kingdom of Bahrain due to the demographics (gender, age and years of experience), while there were differences due to the demographics (qualification and position).

Keywords:- E-Marketing, Competitive Advantage, Reliability, Response, Safety, Kingdom of Bahrain.

I. INTRODUCTION

Marketing has been affected by the great development witnessed by the information and communication technology sector and found its effectiveness on the internet. It is called E-Marketing, which in our time is considered a necessary means that contributes to achieving marketing goals and is considered one of the least expensive marketing (Al-Khalifa, 2019).

In fact, E-Marketing is of great importance, especially at the time of the emergence of new global changes, the growth of the pace of competition, the expansion of freedom in global trade, and the information and communications revolution, which prompted organizations to use it to improve their competitive capabilities (Sweih, 2019). Organizations adopt electronic marketing in their work to raise their effectiveness, increase their efficiency, improve the development of their performance and improve the performance level of employees to achieve customer satisfaction and maintain them, and to increase their market share to realize the competitive advantage (Ali, 2019).

The patchwork of this paper is planned as follows: Literature framework is presented in section (2). Section (3) presents the methodology. Discussion and analysis are explained in section (4), while recommendations are in section (5).

II. LITERATURE FRAMEWORK

A. E-Marketing

➤ Meaning of E-Marketing

E-Marketing is defined as the optimal use of the capabilities of the internet, various communication networks and multiple media, which in turn, contribute to achieving marketing goals with the resulting renewable advantages and multiple possibilities (Riyadi & Sunarsi, 2021; Abdeldayem & Aldulaimi, 2021). It is also defined as the best use of digital technology, including information and communication technologies, to activate the productivity of marketing and its processes, represented in organizational functions, activities and processes directed at determining the needs of the target market and providing services and goods to customers (Al-Huda & Yassin, 2021).

➤ Objectives of E-Marketing

- Improving the mental image of the organization.
- Providing services and improving customer care.
- Searching for new clients.
- Increase customer reach.
- Carry our buying and selling.
- Increasing the scope of the market and moving it from a local market to a global market.
- Trying to meet and fulfill customer expectation.
- Reduce costs.
- Achieving speed in doing business.
- Delivering new value and real benefit to customers (Chahria, 2021).

➤ Importance of E-Marketing

The important of E-Marketing represented in the companies' reliance on internet marketing, which allowed them to display their products in various parts of the world continuously throughout the day and all days of the year, and this gave them a greater opportunity to reap and maximize profits, and in addition to this, they were able to reach more customers. In addition, we find that the preparation and maintenance of e-commerce sites is more economical than building retail markets and installing expensive equipment to be used to customer service. In addition, the organization will not need a large number of employees and only employs computer specialists to facilitate sales and purchases for

customers. Additionally, we find that the internet database keep the dates of buying and selling operations in addition to customer information and does not require the presence of customers to the place of sale, as this extends distances and exceeds the limits (Mohamed & Al-Ashqar, 2018).

B. Institutional Excellence

➤ *Meaning of competitive advantage*

Competitive advantage is defined as the extent to which business organizations are able to produce a product for the customer, but in a distinct way from what other competing organizations offer. Competitive advantage focuses on meeting the needs and wants of customers in terms of product quality, and organizations use advanced production methods and a highly trained work force. Competitive advantage leads to increasing the market share of organizations, increasing their profits and stability in the markets, and breaking into global markets (Abdeldayem & Aldulaimi, 2022; Waer, 2019).

➤ *Importance of competitive advantage*

Competitive advantage is the main weapon for facing market challenges and competing organizations, as it represents a criterion for identifying successful organizations from others, and it is also the catalyst and engine for organizations to enhance their capabilities to occupy a strong position in the markets and obtain a larger market share than competitors (Hamel, 2021).

➤ *Objectives of the competitive advantage*

- Creating value for the organization among its competitors in the market.
- Achieving a large and distinct market share and attracting customers on an ongoing basis.
- Forming external loyalty to the organization and its development in the local, regional and global market, which leads to customer satisfaction and maximizing profits.
- Create a future vision of goals and opportunities for the organizations (Hassan, 2017).

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Problem:

Based on various studies that confirmed the importance of the E-Marketing and its positive impact on achieving the competitive advantage, researchers wanted to identify the impact of E-Marketing (reliability, response and safety) on achieving the competitive advantage at Batelco Company in the Kingdom of Bahrain. The problem of research could therefore be expressed in the following key question:

“What is the impact of E-Marketing (reliability, response and safety) on achieving the competitive advantage at Batelco Company in the Kingdom of Bahrain?”

The main question results in the following sub-questions:

- What is the reality of E-Marketing at Batelco Company in the Kingdom of Bahrain?
- What is the reality of the competitive advantage at Batelco Company in the Kingdom of Bahrain?
- What is the reality of the relationship between E-Marketing and the competitive advantage at Batelco Company in the Kingdom of Bahrain?

B. Research Hypotheses

➤ *Main hypothesis 1:*

H1: There is a positive significant impact for E-Marketing (reliability, response and safety) on achieving the competitive advantage at Batelco Company in the Kingdom of Bahrain.

➤ *Main hypothesis 2:*

H1: There are positive significant differences relating to the impact of E-Marketing (reliability, response and safety) on achieving the competitive advantage at Batelco Company in the Kingdom of Bahrain due to the demographics (gender, age, qualification, years of experience and position).

C. Research Framework

Figure (1) below illustrates the research framework and shows the variables of the research

Fig 1 (Illustration of the research framework)

IV. RESEARCH ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

➤ Analysis of answers to the questionnaire variables

Table 1 Analysis of research community answers to the questionnaire variable (E-Marketing, reliability dimension)

Sr.	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Ranking	Mean Interpretation
1	The company's website is popular with its customers.	4.145	0.775	3	Agree
2	The company's website is rich in information about its services and offers.	4.250	0.774	2	Agree
3	The company sends targeted text messages over the phone.	4.335	0.751	1	Agree
4	The company sends attractive promotion offers via e-mail.	4.135	0.927	5	Agree
5	The company uses the internet to learn about my needs and interests.	4.145	0.846	4	Agree
	Total	4.202			

Results presented in table (1) show that the general average of the variable (E-Marketing, reliability dimension) reached (4.202), which shows that the opinions of the research sample were high of this dimension.

Table 2 Analysis of the research community answers to the questionnaire variable (E-Marketing, response dimension)

Sr.	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Ranking	Mean Interpretation
1	The company's website is multilingual to meet the needs of different customers.	4.242	0.794	2	Agree
2	The company's website provides a quick response.	4.188	0.851	4	Agree
3	The company's website is easy to use and access.	4.250	0.848	1	Agree
4	The company's website is constantly updated with new information.	4.225	0.775	3	Agree
	Total	4.226			Agree

Results displayed in table (2) show that the general average of the variable (E-Marketing, response dimension) reached (4.226), which shows that the opinions of the research sample were high of this dimension.

Table 3 Analysis of the research community answers to the questionnaire variable (E-Marketing, Safety dimension)

Sr.	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Ranking	Mean Interpretation
1	I feel safe when I use the company's website.	4.233	0.840	1	Agree
2	The company's use of new electronic security systems makes me feel reassured in my dealings with it.	4.223	0.790	2	Agree
3	I feel comfortable when I disclose my personal information on the company's website.	4.135	0.935	4	Agree
4	I feel comfortable when I communicate with the company by e-mail.	4.148	0.929	3	Agree
	Total	4.185			Agree

Results displayed in table (3) show that the general average of the variable (E-Marketing, Safety dimension) reached (4.185), which shows that the opinions of the research sample were high of this dimension.

Table 4 Analysis of the research community answers to the questionnaire variable (competitive advantage)

Sr.	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Ranking	Mean Interpretation
1	The company's website helps attract customers that are more new.	4.228	0.838	5	Agree
2	The company provides modern services to its customers.	4.263	0.791	1	Agree
3	The company's prices are attractive and its offers and varied.	4.185	0.945	8	Agree
4	The company's electronic services are distinguished.	4.235	0.754	3	Agree

5	The company's website is reliable and credible.	4.250	0.790	2	Agree
6	The company uses advanced software that facilitates the e-marketing process.	4.235	0.798	4	Agree
7	The company is characterized by a quick response to customer requests.	4.173	0.935	9	Agree
8	The company's excellence helps to face competitive threats.	4.203	0.842	6	Agree
9	The company's website contributes to understanding and knowing the desires of customers.	4.133	0.926	11	Agree
10	The company cares about customers opinions.	4.135	0.929	10	Agree
11	The company's management focuses on understanding the needs of the customer to increase his satisfaction.	4.188	0.908	7	Agree
	Total	4.202			Agree

Results presented in table (4) show that the general average of the variable reached (4.202), which shows that the opinions of the research sample were high of this variable.

D. Testing Research Hypotheses

To make sure that the main hypothesis (1) is correct "There is a positive significant impact for E-Marketing (reliability, response and safety) on achieving the competitive advantage at Batelco Company in the Kingdom of Bahrain.", multiple linear regression analysis were used where the results showed the following:

Table 5 Results of multiple regression analysis of the impact of E-Marketing dimensions on achieving the competitive advantage at Batelco Company in the Kingdom of Bahrain.

Dimension	Correlation co-efficient R	Adjusted R ²	F Value	B value	Beta Value	T value	Significance
Reliability	0.875	0.765	430.830	0.124	0.107	2.515	0.012
Response				0.337	0.314	6.908	0.000
Safety				0.496	0.512	11.743	0.000
Constant				0.179		1.458	0.146

Accordingly, to the results presented above in table (5), the main hypothesis (1) is accepted. In addition, results of the main hypothesis (2), "There are positive significant differences relating to the impact of E-Marketing (reliability, response and safety) on achieving the competitive advantage of Batelco Company in the Kingdom of Bahrain due to the demographics (gender, age, qualification, years of experience and position). They showed that there were no statistically significant differences at the level of (0.05) relating to the demographics (gender, age, and years of experience), while there were differences due to the demographics (qualification and position).

V. CONCLUDING COMMENTS

- The level of application of Batelco Company for E-Marketing came significantly.
- The most applied dimensions of E-Marketing at the company in question was the dimension of response.
- The company in question uses E-Marketing to identify the needs and preferences of its customers.
- The company in question has an informative website that provides quick response to customers.
- E Marketing has contributed in achieving a competitive advantage for the company in question.
- The company's website provides customers with comfort and a sense of security.

In the light of conclusions formulated, the following recommendations were proposed:

- Batelco Company must enhance electronic and digital marketing practices through the adoption of the fourth generation technologies such artificial intelligence, big data, Nano technology, internet of things and 3D printing to achieve more progress over competitors in the telecommunications market.
- The company in question should pay attention to conducting electronic surveys with customers on a regular and continuous basis to measure the level of customer satisfaction and loyalty regarding the quality of its electronic services.
- The company in question should encourage its customers to submit electronic complaints because it is considered an early warning, by allocating an option on the website for receiving and handling customers' complaints, so that experts in this field take care of its management.
- The company should respond to customer requests quickly by providing the necessary capabilities such as providing the latest electronic programs to process customer requests and training employees to use modern technology.
- The company should enhance the confidence of its customers in its website and encourage them to conduct their transactions electronically by making them feel safe and secure in their electronic dealings and giving them

guarantees to make them feel that the company they deal with is trust worthy.

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